

NOVO TESTE

```

11     "https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i
12     "https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/"
13   "potentialAction": {
14     "@type": "SearchAction",
15     "target": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/pages/search_resu
16     "query-input": "required name=search_term"
17   }},
18   {
19     "@context": "https://schema.org/",
20     "@type": "VideoObject",
21     "name": "5 elementos chave na construção de um site",
22     "@id": "https://youtu.be/mLpWVAoKB3A",
23     "datePublished": "2020-01-17",
24     "description": "5 elementos chave na construção de um s
25     "thumbnailURL" : "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-con
26     "thumbnail" : "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-conte
27     "duration" : "11M47S",
28     "uploadDate" : "2020-01-17",
29     "author": {
30       "@type": "Corporation",
31       "name": "Marketing Digital Tools"
32     }
33   },
34 {
35   "@context": "http://schema.org",
36   "@type": "webPage",
37   "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/planos",
38   "mainEntityOfPage": {
39     "@type": "WebPage",
40     "id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/planos/",
41     "name": "Marketing Digital Tools",
42     "description": "Planos e Preços"
43   } },
44 {
45   "@context": "http://schema.org",
46   "@type": "BlogPosting",
47   "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/Blog",
48   "image": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/u
49   "url": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/como-criar-um-
50   "headline": "Como criar um site e-commerce?",
51   "alternativeHeadline": "Marketing Digital Tools explica
52   "dateCreated": "2020-01-23",
53   "datePublished": "2020-01-23",
54   "dateModified": "2020-01-23",
55   "inLanguage": "pt-PT",
56   "isFamilyFriendly": "true",
57   "copyrightYear": "2020",
58   "copyrightHolder": "Marketing Digital Tools",
59   "contentLocation": {
60     "@type": "Place",
61     "name": "Porto, PT"
62   },
63   "accountablePerson": {
64     "@type": "Person",
65     "name": "Sérgio Julião",
66     "url": "http://sergiojuliao.com"
67   },
68   "author": {
69     "@type": "Person",
70     "name": "Sérgio Julião",
71     "url": "http://sergiojuliao.com"
72   },
73   "creator": {
74     "@type": "Person",
75     "name": "Sérgio Julião",
76     "url": "http://sergiojuliao.com"
77   },
78   "publisher": {
79     "@type": "Organization",
80     "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com",
81     "name": "Marketing Digital Tools",
82     "url": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com",
83     "logo": {
84       "@type": "ImageObject",
85     }

```

Detetado em Website

0 ERROS 2 AVISOS 7 ITENS

Website	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	2 AVISOS	1 ITEM
ID: http://marketingdigitaltools.com/Website					
BlogPosting / Organization	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS			1 ITEM
@id			http://marketingdigitaltools.com/Webs		
VideoObject	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS			1 ITEM
name			Marketing Digital Tools		
url			http://marketingdigitaltools.com/		
Service / WebPage	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS			1 ITEM
sameAs			https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/		
sameAs			https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools		
WebSite	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS			1 ITEM
sameAs			https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools		
ProfessionalService	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS			1 ITEM
sameAs			https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFiw/featured		
FAQPage	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS			1 ITEM
potentialAction			4891093/admin/		
@type			SearchAction		
target					
@type			EntryPoint		
urlTemplate			http://marketingdigitaltools.com/pages/search_results?q={search_term}		
query-input					
@type			PropertyValueSpecification		
valueRequired			http://schema.org/True		
valueName			search_term		